

PURCHASE INTENTION OF REAL ESTATE BUYERS IN NAGA CITY USING VIRTUAL STAGING

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the impact of virtual staging on the purchase intentions of real estate buyers and investors in Naga City, Camarines Sur. Specifically, it aimed to assess how demographic profiles influence perceptions of virtual staging across dimensions of convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency; examine the significant relationship between gender, age, and income on these perceptions; and develop a comprehensive virtual staging user guide. Employing a descriptive-quantitative research design, data were collected from 30 participants through convenience sampling using a Likert-scale questionnaire. The results revealed a "very positive" overall impact on purchase intention, evidenced by a combined weighted mean of 3.79. Statistical analysis using Chi-square tests indicated that calculated χ^2 -value < χ^2 -critical value at df and level of significance values for age, gender, and monthly income were lower than critical values, confirming no significant relationship between demographic factors and the perception of virtual staging. This suggests that the technology's influence transcends traditional demographic boundaries, serving as a universally effective marketing tool in the local real estate market. The study concludes that virtual staging significantly enhances purchase intention, providing the empirical basis for the developed user guide. It is recommended that real estate practitioners prioritize high-quality virtual design and immersive experiences to maximize buyer satisfaction and foster long-term market trust. Future research should utilize larger, randomized samples and explore additional variables, such as technological literacy, to further refine the understanding of digital marketing's role in the real estate sector.

Keywords: *Visual appeal, Convenience, Purchase Intention, Real Estate Market, Virtual Staging, Cost-efficiency*

INTRODUCTION

As trends change over time, so does the market's behavior. As noted by Tao et al. (2022), "Consumer purchase behaviors have thus changed greatly, and consumer services companies need to adjust their business models to adapt to this change." The world is increasingly oriented toward technological advancement and relies primarily on the services provided by digitized systems. Hoehe & Thibaut (2020) revealed in their study that roughly 4.57 billion people, which is 59% of the world population, according to recent estimates in 2019, are using the Internet in coping with the daily operations and transactions that life may demand and serve as an entertainment using virtual recreational activities through the use of smartphones, desktops, or tablets. That being said, it is paramount to note that people's way of life is shifting toward a more convenient, accessible approach as technology advances. With this sudden shift in behavior and approach, it is integral to have an in-depth understanding of the extent to which incorporating technological and virtual advancements in the sales process can influence consumer purchase intention.

Purchase Intention refers to the subjective tendency to purchase products or services, or a conscious decision to select preferred products or services, which may influence a person's purchasing decisions (Li et al., 2022). Purchase intention is considered a dependent variable that can manifest and be measured in response to several internal and/or external factors. Hence, it is a measure of one's attitude or behavior towards purchasing or availing a product or service (MBA Skool Team, n.d.). In fact, purchase intention is an integral aspect in the metric in marketing. In this context, intent marketing is the practice of targeting consumers with goods and services based on their intentions to accept, purchase, or use a specific product or service, even when the company or brand has not explicitly acknowledged those intentions. Accordingly, purchase intention, as a metric, is effective for measuring activity and productivity. A customer's intent can make it straightforward to determine precisely which type of material should be delivered in an advertisement.

Thus, purchase intention plays a pivotal role in measuring marketing productivity and profitability, as it is used as a metric to increase return on investment in marketing. There is a myriad of factors that can trigger and affect the purchase intention of a customer, may it either be an internal or external factor. The following are the most prevalent factors that affects a customer's purchase intention: (1) Seasonality; (2) Existing customer satisfaction; (3) Customer demographics, and; (4) Advertising. (Market Research Solutions, n.d.).

Integrating virtual reality technology and applications into the selling and/or buying process can be highly influential on customers' buying intentions by making the selection process more valuable, enjoyable, convenient, and accessible (Salem, 2023). Virtual

staging is a digital tool for enhancing property images, making them more desirable to potential purchasers. It is affordable, saves time, and improves online property listings. This is one form of virtual reality technology that some real estate companies use to reduce time and costs associated with preparing a home for staging. Traditionally, to properly assess and purchase a property, buyers typically schedule an on-site visit to evaluate the property and determine whether it meets their preferences and is suitable for purchase. On the other hand, due to advances in technology and software applications over the years, and the recent COVID-19 pandemic, which accelerated digitalization worldwide, virtual staging has emerged as an alternative to home staging. The ease of seeing homes online and in a 3D form, which can make a customer feel like they are in the actual property, has contributed to the growing popularity of virtual staging. It enables realtors to highlight properties in their best light without the need for physical furnishings, which is particularly useful when in-person viewing is difficult.

As the real estate market accelerates in 2023, it has become increasingly challenging for companies, agents, and brokers to satisfy the rising demand from buyers, especially those from outside the area. To address this surge in demand, virtual staging has emerged as an essential tool in real estate. By enhancing a home's visual appeal without in-person visits, virtual staging increases exposure and boosts the likelihood of a sale. It helps potential buyers better imagine their living arrangements, providing a convenient solution for both real estate professionals and property seekers (Guangzhou, 2025). Additionally, a study identifies ten components, presents a five-layered interpretive structure, and demonstrates the causal relationship between VR stores and purchase intention. According to the study, e-service quality is the most important element determining purchase intention in a virtual reality store (Mkedder, et.al., 2024).

Therefore, this study sought to find out various determinants of virtual staging that influence the purchase intention of a client, which is based on the demographic profile of the respondents. It is also essential to determine the impact of virtual staging on the purchase intention of potential clients. Analyzing the buyer perception of the properties that integrate virtual staging is discussed, emphasizing the buyer's preferences in space, such as size, layout, and potential for customization, and how this translates to purchase intent. This aims to elucidate the impact of virtual staging on the purchase intention for real estate properties. To properly guide the paper in achieving the aforementioned objectives of the study, the following factors are tackled and discussed: (1) Demographic profile of the subjects; (2) Perception of the participants in using virtual staging influencing their purchase intention; (3) Significant relationship between the purchase intention towards virtual staging and the respondent's demographic profile, and; (4) Output of the study. This will mainly revolve around real estate companies, commercial or residential, realtors and real estate agents, and property owners who own one or more properties, and a real estate investor who owns a wide range of properties.

With that, the findings and results of this paper are beneficial to real estate companies, providing an in-depth overview of the buyer's perception of new approaches and methods in property selling, as well as an opportunity to save expenses. This paper is helpful in real estate investors and property owners, especially when they are growing their

portfolios, providing them an alternative, easy, cost-efficient investment evaluation of the property and giving them a glimpse of the perception of the potential buyers. Finally, this is useful for the real estate industry in general, as it provides insight into changes in market behavior.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to assess the influence of virtual staging on real estate buyers' purchase intentions. To do so, this sought to address these objectives:

1. To determine how the buyer's profile impacts their perception of virtual staging in property purchases, in terms of gender, age, profession, marital status, monthly income, property owned, tenure, and financing platform.
2. To assess the perception of the potential buyers on the purchase intention of real estate property along convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency.
3. To determine the significant relationship between the buyer's gender, age, and monthly income and the perception of potential buyers.
4. To develop a virtual staging user guide to aid in the purchase intention of the real estate buyers.

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the tools, approaches, and methods utilized in this study to gather, collate, and interpret the data that is needed in this study. This section discusses the research design, methods and procedures, respondent's profile, ethical considerations, and data analysis technique employed in this study that provides an in-depth explanation of how data was collected and interpreted to form a valuable conclusion.

Research Design

This study uses both qualitative data such as respondent's perspectives and demographic profile and quantitative data through the design of the questionnaire and statistical tools used to present the data gathered. This is the reason why this study employs a mixed-methods research design, using both quantitative and qualitative tools and data. Using the two known research designs ensures that more accurate data and conclusions can be obtained and interpreted for the study. In this study, qualitative data collection procedures were used to obtain the necessary information.

Gradually, these data were used to support the researchers' goals, using graphical representations and numerical data to interpret the data and provide evidence-based findings and conclusions.

The qualitative data mainly consisted of the demographic profile of the respondents, which was included in the first category of the questionnaire, as well as the respondents' perspectives, which were covered in the second category. The qualitative data were

derived from the design of the questionnaire, which aimed to collate and interpret responses in the second category using a Likert scale. This scale involved respondents rating their level of agreement, with each level assigned a corresponding numerical score, making the data quantifiable. Through tabular presentation and the use of statistical tools, quantitative data were also utilized, making the study suitable for a convergent parallel mixed-methods research design.

Respondents/Participants of the Study

This study focuses on real estate owners and investors within the province of Camarines Sur, specifically in Naga City. The respondents come from various age brackets, genders, occupations, marital statuses, and employment statuses, which collectively reflect their overall demographic profile. To properly filter the respondents, this paper employs non probability sampling specifically, availability sampling, also known as convenience sampling. This sampling design was chosen because the participants were in proximity to the study site.

Property owners and investors typically have busy schedules, so availability sampling was the most suitable approach, especially since the survey was administered online. As the number of respondents depended on the availability of the respondents, the study accumulated a total of thirty (30) participants. There has been a huge consideration given to the time, availability, and accessibility of the questionnaires to the respondents that the study only accumulated an ample number of participants. This also shows how property owners and investors are used in using the internet and new software and websites which can tell how already adept they are in advanced technology. Respondents were of different profession, age, gender, and property owned which makes their perspectives and opinions diverse making an unbiased result for this study. All the respondents haven't also used a virtually staged property in their entire property search journey so this study also has a clear insight on how the potentiality of virtual staging in Naga City can affect the purchase intention of real estate property buyers.

Data Gathering Tools

This study utilized several qualitative data gathering tools such as secondary data and survey questionnaire. Secondary data through related studies and literature are beneficial in drafting the thesis questionnaire. The survey has been more specific and accurate, as the respondent's profile suggests that they need a more direct-to-the-point form to save time. This study used an online Google Forms survey posted to the different property groups to gather information from the appropriate and available respondents. Through this, questionnaires can still be accessible to property owners and investors who are busy with their own work/business. Pen-and-paper survey questionnaires were also distributed, with the researcher's knowledge of respondents' property ownership. The research questionnaire is composed of two parts. The first one is to gather the necessary information regarding the respondent's profiles, such as age, sex, profession, etc.

The second part was composed of statements that are sub-categorized into four to accurately get the perspectives of the respondents based on the following factors: convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency. This part is in line with the 5-Point Likert Scale design to accurately determine the level of agreeableness and purchase intention of the buyers/respondents.

This study also employs a type of non-probability sampling which is the convenience sampling for the respondent selection process. Convenience sampling is a way of selecting participants from the target population based on ease of access (Golzar, et.al., 2022). In the context of this study, the number of respondents who answered both the online survey and pen-and-paper questionnaire depends on the availability of the respondents. This sampling method is the most suitable in the study's design as most of the respondents are employed and business owner who has a busy schedule and it would take a lot of time to make an appointment to each one of them. Through convenience sampling, it allows the respondents to answer the questionnaire with ease and comfort as they are not put into pressure in answering the questionnaire.

To properly present the data gathered, it is presented in tabular form and employs the frequency and percentage method to better interpret the quantitative data. This is mostly used to present the demographic profile and the perspective of the respondents regarding the convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency of using virtual staging in their property search and how it can affect their intention to purchase. Descriptive statistics, through determining the overall weighted mean of every category, help in accurately interpreting the numerical data presented in the table. Additionally, Chi-Square Test is a statistical tool that was also utilized to determine the significant relationship of the buyer's profile to their perspective and purchase intention. The purpose of this test is to determine if a difference between observed data and expected data is due to chance, or if it is due to a relationship between the variables you are studying (University of Southampton, n.d.).

Data Gathering Procedure

This paper incorporates various methods of gathering data through primary and secondary data analysis and a survey questionnaire to properly achieve the main objective of this study in relation to the demographic profile of the participants, their perception of virtual staging in terms of convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency which helps determine the purchase intention of the participants.

The respondents of this study were professionals so it is imperative to be considerate of their consent, time, and ease in answering the questionnaire. Hence, this study employed two platforms to gather data from the target respondents which is through the online survey and the traditional survey process through pen and paper. The survey questionnaire revolves around two (2) parts. The first part contains data on the respondent's demographics. The second part was a 5-point Likert Scale to properly assess the convenience, satisfaction, and effectiveness of visual aesthetics in virtual staging, which would affect their buying decision through heightened purchase intention.

The questions and situations stated herein are based on the researcher's ideas, thoughts, and observations. Developed in 1932 by Rensis Likert, Likert Scale is used to measure attitudes which typically is a 5- or 7-point ordinal scale used by respondents to rate the degree to which they agree or disagree with a statement (Sullivan & Artino, 2013).

On the other hand, to ensure the confidentiality of the data the respondents gave, it is imperative to get their consent through signing the consent form before answering the questionnaire. The consent form is composed of the researcher's academic profile and the background of the study so the respondents would get the gist of why and how the study will work.

The questionnaires were also spread out through the personal Facebook profile of the researcher and to the property listings page available on Facebook. In order to post on this platform, one needs to be a member of the page first. The researcher is a member of these platforms before posting. The admin usually filters out the post, and as long as one follows the page protocols set by the page admin, there is no harm in posting there. Members of that page were mostly homeowners and business owners who have a commercial building they are renting or are trying to rent out. Hence, this community is the perfect group of population for a respondent.

Data Analysis Techniques

This study has a primary purpose of determining the purchase intention of the real estate property buyers in buying a property when virtual staging is introduced in their property search journey. With that, this paper sought to find out the buyer's profile, the perspective of the participants based on the four following factors such as the convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency, the significant relationship of the first two objectives, and the possible output of this study that can aid in presenting and introducing virtual staging in the mentioned area.

In able to do so, this study is designed to utilize the mixed-method design and tools in gathering data and information from the available respondents. These data-gathering instruments were a survey questionnaire and data analysis to properly achieve the goal of the data-gathering process. Additionally, descriptive statistics was also employed that allows the gathered data and information to be collated in a tabular and graphical form and shows the frequency and percentage to accurately correlate the data from the demographic profile of the respondents to its perception in using virtual staging in its property search to accurately and adequately get the influences of virtual staging in the purchase intention of potential buyers of real estate property. It can be used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research.

Gradually, this study uses these collated data and information to form a valuable findings and conclusion which can be beneficial for the real estate property buyers and investors alike, real estate companies — may it be a residential or commercial property, and to the advancement of real estate processes and procedures in Naga City which can eventually

help in the growth of its economy, especially that the industrial development is one of the reasons for the economy growth of the city.

Finally, with the result obtained in this study, the final output would be the virtual staging user-guide which can aid in the purchase intention of the real estate buyers as it can provide an information and direction on how to use virtual staging platforms in their property search journey.

RESULTS

Table 1
Respondent's Profile

n=30		
Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	17	57%
Female	13	43%
<i>Age</i>		
20-29	10	33%
30-39	12	40%
40-49	5	17%
50-60	2	7%
60-70	1	3%
<i>Profession</i>		
BPO Employee	2	7%
Corporate/Private Employee	14	47%
Government Employee	6	20%
Seafarer	2	7%
Businessman	5	17%
Self-employed	1	3%
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	15	50%
Married	14	47%
Separated	1	3%
<i>Monthly Income</i>		
P 20,000 - P 40,000	16	53%
P 50,000 - P 70,000	7	23%
P 80,000 - P 100,000	4	13%
P 200,000 above	3	10%
<i>Property Owned</i>		
Primary Residence	13	43%
Secondary Residence	7	23%

Ancestral/Family Home	4	13%
Investment Property	5	17%
Renting an Apartment	1	3%
<i>Tenure</i>		
Less than a year	3	10%
1-10 years	14	47%
11-30 years	13	43%
<i>Financing Platform</i>		
Salary	8	27%
PAG-IBIG Financing	10	33%
Existing Business/Investment	6	20%
Commercial Bank Financing	5	17%
Cash	1	3%

Table 2
Buyer's Perception regarding Virtual Staging in terms of Convenience

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Easy to gather sufficient information about real estate properties online.	3.63	Agree	4
2. Current methods of viewing properties (e.g., photos, physical visits) are convenient.	4.13	Agree	1
3. Scheduling physical visits to properties is time-consuming.	2.73	Moderately Agree	5
4. Prefer a more time-efficient way of viewing multiple properties.	4.1	Agree	2
5. Current property listings provide enough convenience for buyers	3.73	Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.67	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 Strongly Agree, 3.41 – 4.20 Agree, 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree, 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree, 1.0 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 3
Buyer's Perception regarding Virtual Staging in terms of Satisfaction

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Satisfied with the amount of information provided in traditional property listings.	3.3	Moderately Agree	4
2. Trusts what can be seen in property photos when evaluating a listing.	2.77	Moderately Agree	5
3. Often feel uncertain about how the property will look in real life.	4.17	Agree	1
4. Satisfied with the overall buying experience when using traditional property search methods.	3.5	Agree	2
5. Satisfied with the current presentation of properties available for sale.	3.43	Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.43	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 Strongly Agree, 3.41 – 4.20 Agree, 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree, 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree, 1.0 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 4
Buyer's Perception regarding Virtual Staging in terms of Visual Appeal

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Appearance of a property in listing photos influences their initial interest.	4.43	Strongly Agree	1
2. Often find it hard to imagine what an empty or unfinished space would look like when furnished.	3.53	Agree	4

3. The visual presentation of a property dramatically affects their impression of its value.	4.13	Agree	2
4. Prefer properties that look visually appealing in photos, even if they are not fully furnished.	3.4	Moderately Agree	5
5. Think better-styled or decorated listings are more attractive to potential buyers.	4.03	Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.9	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 Strongly Agree, 3.41 – 4.20 Agree, 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree, 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree, 1.0 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 5
Buyer's Perception regarding Virtual Staging in terms of Cost-Efficiency

Statement	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Virtual staging is a more cost-efficient option compared to traditional physical staging.	4.43	Strongly Agree	1
2. Using virtual staging reduces unnecessary expenses in property marketing.	3.53	Agree	4
3. The cost of virtual staging is reasonable given its potential impact on attracting buyers.	4.13	Agree	2
4. Virtual staging helps sellers/agents maximize property presentation while minimizing costs.	3.4	Moderately Agree	5

5. Believed that virtual staging offers better value for money compared to traditional staging methods.	4.03	Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.9	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 Strongly Agree, 3.41 – 4.20 Agree, 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree, 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree, 1.0 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 6
Buyer’s Perspective of Virtual Staging affecting their Purchase Intention

Areas	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Rank
Convenience	3.67	Agree	3
Satisfaction	3.43	Agree	4
Visual Appeal	3.9	Agree	1
Cost-efficiency	3.7	Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.79	Agree	

Legend: 4.21 – 5.0 Strongly Agree, 3.41 – 4.20 Agree, 2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Agree, 1.81 – 2.60 Disagree, 1.0 – 1.80 Strongly Disagree

Table 7
Significant relationship of the buyer’s gender, age, and monthly income profile to their perception of virtual staging

Gender					
Gender/ Perception	Computed x ² Value	Degree of freedom	x ² critical value at a=0.05	Interpretation	Decision
Convenience	2.81	2	5.99	Without significant relationship	Accept H ₀
Satisfaction	2.24	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H ₀
Visual Appeal	2.51	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H ₀

Cost-efficiency	1.44	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Age					
Convenience	0.1	2	5.99	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Satisfaction	3.96	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Visual Appeal	1.88	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Cost-efficiency	1.53	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Monthly Income					
Convenience	1.3	2	5.99	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Satisfaction	1.13	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Visual Appeal	5.45	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o
Cost-efficiency	1.94	3	7.81	Without significant relationship	Accept H _o

*If the computed χ^2 -value < χ^2 -critical value at df and level of significance; Accept H_o; and
If the computed χ^2 -value > χ^2 -critical value at df and level of significance; Reject H_o*

DISCUSSION

This section presents the qualitative and quantitative results and data necessary for formulating the conclusion. Data was collated in tabular form, and results and findings were discussed. This section shows the buyer's profile by showing the demographic profile of the respondents. This also indicates the tabular presentation of the survey results on respondents' perceptions of virtual staging in their property searches. It can be analyzed in terms of convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, cost-efficiency, and purchase intention.

Research Objective 1: To determine how the buyer's profile impacts their perception of virtual staging in property purchases.

1. The demographics of the participants shows that most of them were male, but it still comes close to the percentage of women participants.
2. Significant number of participants were between 30 and 39 and the least population who participated in the study were aged from 60-70 years old.
3. Property buyers and investors in this study were mostly employed in a private company. Least percentage were categorized as 'self-employed'.
4. The majority of the participants were still single. Only one of the participant were separated from their partners.

5. Prominent number of participants earned between Php 20,000 and Php 40,000 per month and only three of the participants were earning 200,000 pesos monthly.
6. Most of the respondents also owned a residential property that serves as their primary dwelling and only the least percent of the population is renting a residential property.
7. Majority of the respondent's tenure in their houses also lies under 1-10 years. Meanwhile there is only a slight gap where participants answered that they already have the property for 11-30 years now and only few just recently had their property recently.
8. It must also be noted that PAG-IBIG financing as a form of property financing is still the most used platform in acquiring a property up until this date and only the least percentage of the participant said that they paid for their property on cash.

Research Objective 2: To assess the perception of the potential buyers on the purchase intention of real estate property along convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency:

1. Convenience was rated highly with a mean of 3.67, which indicates that respondents 'Agree' that virtual staging brings convenience to their property search journey. The majority of respondents' responses in this category fall between 'Agree' and 'Moderately Agree,' suggesting that they acknowledge that virtual staging may make their property search more convenient.
2. Satisfaction category had the lowest weighted mean of 3.43, closest to 'Moderately Agree' compared to the rest of the category. Participants are neither satisfied nor unsatisfied when images of the virtually arranged property are presented to them, implying that the participants are not yet prepared to adopt this method in the real estate market.
3. The highest weighted mean was in the category of Visual Appeal, which received a weighted mean of 3.9 ('Agree'). The importance of visual presentation is paramount, indicating that the aesthetic quality of the virtual staging is a major driver of purchase intent. There is only a tiny difference in their confidence between digitally staged and traditionally staged properties because it has never been used before.
4. Cost-efficiency, with an overall weighted mean of 3.7 was also ranked highly falling into 'Agree' as an interpretation of the Likert-scale. Respondents agreed that virtual staging saves more money than traditional staging and is more cost-effective for sellers and brokers, allowing them to make the best use of virtual staging and augmented reality tours when showing their properties. These characteristics improve potential buyers' desire to purchase a digitally staged property, since this generation is more interested in how new technology can make their life easier and give a convenient, cost-effective experience.

Research Object 3: To determine the significant relationship between the buyer's profile and the perception of potential buyers.

The result of the study shows that the demographic profile of the respondents such as gender, age, and monthly do not have a significant relationship with their perception regarding virtual staging in terms of convenience, satisfaction, visual appeal, and cost-efficiency having the result of all the factors as χ^2 -value being less than the χ^2 -critical value at df and level of significance.

Research Objective 4: To develop a virtual staging user guide to aid in the purchase intention of the real estate buyers.

The overall information is consistent with the individual data shown. The respondents prioritized the visual appeal of virtual staging, indicating that it can affect the intention to purchase a house. In addition to the cost-effectiveness of the procedure, they may find it easier and more convenient to search for properties via virtual staging. However, the findings show that when it comes to satisfaction, respondents were largely in accord. It is undeniable that property buyers' trust and confidence must be earned through firsthand experience and by giving a high-value experience that results in high satisfaction when employing virtual staging in their property search.

This shows that with proper and slow introduction of virtual staging to the property buyers can eventually aid in their intention to purchase a property. Therefore, this study's final output would be a virtual staging user-guide which can aid the property buyers and real estate companies alike on how to use the virtual staging in their property search journey and providing them an actual experience on how can this advanced technology can help them save time, effort, and money but still get the result and property they want.

Conclusions

This section provides a summary of the key findings of this study. This reflects the overall findings per research objectives and hypotheses, addressing its implications and interpretations.

1. Demographic of the property buyers indicates that interest in property ownership is increasing among younger adults and still single. Additionally, despite modest incomes, many already own or are in the process of acquiring property, suggesting that accessible financing options and payment schemes are helping younger buyers enter the market earlier than previous generations. Most of the real estate property buyers have just recently acquired the property which tallies to the majority of age bracket of the respondents which is 30-39 years old.

This means that property buyers lean forward on buying their first residential property first, before acquiring a property for investment such as commercial and hotel and restaurant properties. This is an advantage for the residential real estate companies to cultivate more projects that aligns with the residential demands of the buyers.

One of the integral parts is the role and availability of a multitude of financings platforms available these days aside from PAG-IBIG which as bank loans and financing, cooperatives, and private lending companies that is prevalent nowadays. In addition to this, companies were also developing real estate projects that are getting more affordable through staggered payments and least amount of downpayments which makes the Filipino people feel that the property they want is reachable. The data support the idea that the digital generation is steadily shaping and, to some extent, redefining the real estate market, making virtual staging a timely and relevant innovation.

2. Virtual staging delivers the efficient, detailed, and outstanding landscape that property purchasers require when purchasing a house. The simplicity of virtual staging in property searches saves purchasers a lot of time and effort. However, the results elicit a bit of doubt among the respondents whether they will be more confident in acquiring a property using virtual staging, as the majority of them have never utilized it in their property searches. One of the factors affecting this is the non-exposure and the lack of knowledge of the respondents regarding virtual staging and how it is used in the real estate market.

Although the results may indicate that participants do not specifically disagree with the notion that virtual staging can provide a satisfactory level of improvement to their property search experience, it is worth noting that the majority of them are still unsure whether this is effective and efficient in their property search. While virtual staging is convenient and cost-effective, it may fall short of giving a physical experience.

The high ratings for Visual Appeal indicate strong market interest in this technology, consistent with global trends in which Virtual Reality (VR) is transforming engagement. The data also indicate that successful adoption and high conversion rates depend heavily on the perceived quality and experience provided by the virtual staging design, necessitating an exemplary approach by real estate companies and agencies. This concludes that respondents believe the visual aesthetics of virtual staging are beneficial in attracting potential buyers' attention in acquiring a house.

This result and findings imply that respondents understand that employing virtual staging in their property search process saves money for them, the company, as well as the brokers and sellers. These characteristics improve potential buyers' desire to purchase a digitally staged property, since this

generation is more interested in how new technology can make their life easier and give a convenient, cost-effective experience. Hence, it is inferred that a cost-efficient design and system of virtual staging can impact the purchase intention of real estate property buyers.

3. This suggests that virtual staging can be considered as a worldwide marketing technique, rather than one that only caters to specific age groups, genders, or income levels. The findings imply that virtual staging strategies do not require considerable demographic segmentation based on age, gender, or income, as their perceived usefulness and influence on purchase intention are similar across varied buyer profiles.

Recommendations

This section provides practical applications of the results and findings and how it these can be implemented. It should suggest policy changes or implemented.

1. Future research should include additional regions and employ broader number of participants and sampling techniques to understand better the acceptance and influence of virtual staging across different markets. The evolving age of the property buyers must be studied in a separate study to show how age can be associated with the marketing strategy that real estate company should use in order to sell more properties. Future researchers needs to further explore the specific niches of the self-employed property buyers/investors in order to examine how their endeavors enable them to purchase a property.

The relationship of marital status must be separately studies as it can greatly affect the purchasing power of a property buyer. It must be studied how monthly can be correlated with the decision to purchase a property because property investors has a tendency to invest in a property that they do not own but still accumulates high profit through sublease agreements. Some property owners tend to rent as their primary home and have their property investment turn into a business. Hence, this strategy can be studied separately. Property owners tend to buy and sell property to earn higher profit and to expand their portfolios, hence this must be studied because real estate companies can learn a lot from unfolding this kind of business/strategy. It is important to further the study the direct influence of the available financing platforms and determine if this has a significant relationship with the growing real estate demands in today's generation.

2. This study suggests for the real estate companies who are going to invest in Naga, City to design a more convenient system or application for the users of virtual staging. This could be in a form of a website that can easily be accessible to most the users. The website is also suggested to be clearer and without any unnecessary process or 'clicks' to provide ease and convenience to the users. This study also comes up with a virtual staging user-guide output which can be

helpful in providing convenience and ease of use to future and first-time users of virtual staging. With that, this study is only limited to the general definition of convenience, in which the future researchers might want to delve deeper such as the specific design and factors contributing to the convenience of the buyers directly affecting their purchase intention.

The study recommends that future initiatives focus on improving buyer satisfaction by delivering outstanding design and experience. Since this research was conducted before virtual staging became common in Naga City, future studies should evaluate buyer satisfaction among system users to confirm its long-term success and address the current gap in comprehensive buyer satisfaction. This paper also provides a reminder that designs should not be unduly elaborate and must adhere to the property's exact specifications in order to balance purchasers' expectations.

It is essential to investigate various augmented realities, such as 3D tours, VR headsets, and other advanced technologies that can be introduced into the city and alter people's impressions of virtual staging and the advanced real estate process. Respondents are already aware of the benefits of virtual staging and almost agree with them, but they remain adamant due to confidence and satisfaction issues, which can be addressed through additional research on a more engaging and conducive approach to presenting virtually staged properties.

3. This proposes delving deeper and conducting additional study on other parameters that may be related to the influence of demographic profile on buyer purchasing intentions. It is also recommended for the real estate market researchers to use this study and other related studies mentioned in observing that age, gender, and monthly income cannot be considered as hindrance in advancing the marketing and operational system in the real estate industry.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The confidentiality of the research participants were taken into account by the researchers. To maintain and protect the respondents' privacy, the researchers adhered to the rules outlined in R.A. No. 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (DPA). As a result, they refrained from disclosing any personal information about the participants. Additionally, the facts and conclusions of this study were not overstated to achieve the researchers' goals. The researchers avoided using any vulgar, derogatory, or discriminatory language in this publication or even in the surveys. Lastly, Researchers properly cited their work in the text or in the references to prevent plagiarism, including papers, articles, or other studies.

Researcher also made sure that the respondents fully understood the purpose of the study through issuing a consent form designed to input a knowledge of what the study is and how their inputs will be used in the formulation of the conclusion

of the study. This study prioritized respondent's ease and comfort and considered the respondent's time and consent in answering the questionnaire. To ensure the respondent's ease of answering the questionnaire, it was accessible online and can be answered anytime and anywhere by the respondents.

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